

Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice on the Use of Seatbelts Among Commercial Bus Drivers in Makurdi Metropolis, Benue State.

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ABSTRACT

Background: Road traffic injuries are major public health problems and a leading cause of death and injury around the world. One of the safest choices drivers and passengers can make is to buckle up. The use of a seatbelt is a proven effective measure in reducing the risk of fatal and non-fatal injuries in the event of a crash. This study aimed to determine the level of knowledge, attitude, and practice of seatbelt use among commercial bus drivers in Makurdi Metropolis.

Methods: A descriptive cross-sectional study was done using a multistage sampling method to select 173 respondents. A self-administered structured questionnaire was administered to study participants. Data collected from respondents was analyzed using SPSS version 23.

Results: The study found that 70% of the participants displayed good knowledge of seatbelts, 72% have a positive attitude score, while 57% have a fair practice on the use of seatbelts.

Conclusion: Government and non-governmental organizations should launch more targeted campaigns aimed at commercial drivers, focusing on the safety benefits of seatbelts and addressing misconceptions about their use. Education campaign programs on seatbelt use, stronger law enforcement, and incentive programs to encourage seatbelt usage

Keywords: Attitude, Benue, Knowledge, Makurdi, Practice, Road Traffic Accident, Seatbelt

INTRODUCTION

Road traffic injuries are major public health problems and a leading cause of death and injury around the world.¹ One of the safest choices drivers and passengers can make is to buckle up.² Traffic collision, also known as a motor vehicle collision, or car crash, occurs when a vehicle collides with another vehicle, pedestrian, animal, road debris, or other moving or

stationary obstruction, such as a tree, pole, or building.³ Traffic collisions often result in injury, disability, death, and property damage as well as financial costs to both society and the individuals involved.³

Several factors contribute to the risk of collision, including vehicle design, operating speed, road design, weather, road environment, driving skills, impairment from alcohol or drugs, and, notably, aggressive driving, distracted driving, speeding, and street racing.³ Seatbelt

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is an effective safety tool that not only saves lives, but also significantly reduces the severity of the injury that a vehicle occupant may have sustained if they were not wearing the device¹. More public enlightenment is needed to increase awareness and compliance with seatbelt use among Nigerian motorists.¹ Policymakers across all levels of government must acknowledge the escalating issue as a public health emergency and develop targeted policy solutions, ensuring rigorous implementation to effectively address the crisis.⁴

Road traffic accidents are a significant public health and safety issue globally and locally, with commercial bus drivers being a particularly vulnerable group due to their frequent exposure to road traffic. In Nigeria, many fatalities and injuries from RTAs occur in the public transport sector. Seatbelts have proven to reduce the severity of injuries and fatalities in the event of an accident. Thus, understanding the knowledge, attitude, and practice of seatbelt use among commercial drivers is essential for improving road safety.

Knowledge and attitudes are often determinants of behaviour. Understanding the drivers' knowledge of the benefits of seatbelts, their attitudes towards using them, and their actual practices can provide insight into the factors that influence seatbelt usage. This knowledge can help in designing targeted interventions that improve compliance with road safety regulations.

The study aimed to determine the knowledge, attitude, and practice of the use of seatbelts among commercial bus drivers in Makurdi, Benue State.

METHODOLOGY

This study was carried out in Makurdi, the capital of Benue State in Nigeria. The name of the state originates from the River Benue, which is the second-longest river in Nigeria. Makurdi was established in 1927 and currently has an estimated population of 490,000. The Tiv are the predominant indigenous ethnic group in Makurdi, followed by the Idoma and Igede speaking groups. Most of the population are civil servants, followed closely by farmers, who practice subsistence agriculture and fishing. Makurdi connects the north and southern parts of the country, serving as a major

transport hub for travelers. Therefore, there are several transport companies such as Benue Links, Pleasure Travels, Flight, Victoria Travels, Zaamo Transport, Valgee Transport Company, to name a few. These commercial bus services link Makurdi to neighbouring states like Enugu, Nassarawa, Abuja, Cross River, and Kogi States.

Study Design

This was a descriptive cross-sectional study.

Study Population

The study population was commercial bus drivers in various motor parks within Makurdi metropolis.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Commercial bus drivers in Makurdi metropolis who give consent to participate in the study
2. Commercial bus drivers in Makurdi metropolis aged 18-65 years
3. Commercial bus drivers in Makurdi metropolis with at least one year of driving experience

Exclusion Criteria

Commercial bus drivers in Makurdi metropolis with chronic illness or on sick leave

Sample Size Determination

The minimum sample will be determined using the formula ($n = z^2pd/d^2$)

Where: n = minimum sample size

Z = standard normal deviation at 95% confidence interval, which corresponds to 1.96

P = estimated prevalence from a previous study = 0.273⁶⁵

Q = complementary probability = (1-p) = 1 - 0.273 = 0.727

d = degree of precision = 0.05

$n = (1.96)^2 \times 0.273 \times 0.727 / (0.05)^2$

n = 304.97

For population size less than 10,000 using Taro Yamane formula

$n = N / (1 + N(e)^2)^{70}$

Where n: is the required sample size from the population under study

N is the whole population under study

e is the precision or sampling error

$$n = N / (1 + N(e)^2)$$

Where N=304.97

e=0.05

$$n = 304.97 / (1 + 304.97(0.05)^2)$$

$$n = 304.97 / (1 + 304.97(0.00025))$$

$$n = 304.97 / 1.76245$$

$$n = 173.039 \approx 173 \text{ drivers}$$

Sampling Technique

A multi-stage sampling technique was used for the study. In the first stage, eleven motor parks in Makurdi metropolis were listed. Of these, six were selected by a simple random technique via balloting. A stratified sampling technique was applied to select the drivers within each selected park. A sampling frame of commercial bus drivers in each of the six selected parks was compiled, and the drivers were stratified based on relevant categories, including gender, age group, years of driving experience, and type of vehicle driven. The number of drivers selected from each park was proportionate to the total number of drivers at the park. This ensured that the sample from each park was representative of the park's total number of drivers.

Data Collection

A structured interviewer-administered questionnaire was used to obtain the following information: Socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents, as well as knowledge, attitudes, and practices of the use of seatbelts. Data collection took place over one week. Participants were approached during breaks or after completing their trips. The purpose of the study was explained to them, and consent was obtained before they participated.

Data Analysis

Collected data was checked for appropriateness, completeness, validation, and accuracy, and was

analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23. Results were presented in tables and charts. Measures of dispersion and central tendency for normally distributed and skewed variables were also determined.

Ethical Consideration

Ethical clearance was sought from the Research and Ethics Committee of the College of Health Sciences, Benue State University (CREC/UGP/145). The nature, purpose, and process of the study were explained to the respondents after which informed verbal consent was obtained from those who agreed to participate in the study.

RESULTS

Of the 173 respondents, almost identical proportions were aged 31-40 years and 41 – 50 years, making up 38.7% and 34.7% respectively. All the drivers were males, and 83.2% of the respondents were married. A high proportion of the respondents (91.3%) were Christians, and most drivers are Tiv (48%). Almost two-thirds (64.7%) of the respondents were SSCE holders, and more drivers (41.6%) had been driving for at least 10 years. It also shows that just above two-thirds (69.9%) of the drivers understand that seatbelt use is very effective in preventing injuries during an accident, while above two-thirds (68.2%) know that the potential consequence of not wearing a seatbelt while driving is an increased risk of injury/death. Similarly, close to three-quarters (72.3%) of the drivers understand that it is a legal requirement for commercial drivers to use a seat belt at all times.

The commercial bus drivers think that wearing a seatbelt is necessary (80.9%) while 63.6% of the respondents wear seatbelts for safety reasons. Despite some reservations about seatbelt use enforcement by some drivers, 77.5% support the idea, and 70.5% opined that seatbelt use should be made mandatory for both the driver and passengers in commercial vehicles. Although 94.8% of the participants have a seat belt in their vehicles, only 60.7% of the drivers always use it.

Table 1: Socio-demographic Characteristic of the Respondents

Variables	Frequency N=173	Percentage %
Age		
20 – 30	17	9.8
31 – 40	67	38.7
41 – 50	60	34.7
51 -60	21	12.1
61 and above	8	4.6
Sex		
Male	173	100
Female	0	0
Marital status		
Single	19	11.0
Married	144	83.2
Widow(er)	0	0
Cohabiting	3	1.7
Separated	5	2.9
Divorce	2	1.2
Religion		
Christianity	158	91.3
Islam	13	7.5
Others	2	1.2
Tribe		
Tiv	83	48.0
Idoma	58	33.5
Others	32	18.5
Highest level of education		
FSLE	28	16.2
SSCE	112	64.7
Diploma	19	11.0
Graduate	9	5.2
Post Graduate	5	2.9
Years of driving experience		
Less than 5years	9	5.2
5-10 years	53	30.6
10 - 20 years	72	41.6
Above 20 years	39	22.5
Type of vehicle		
Coaster Bus	9	5.2
18 -seater Bus	86	49.7
Picnic Bus	62	35.8
Others	16	9.2
Route type		
Within Makurdi Metropolis	19	11.0
Long Distance Travel	154	89.0

Table 2: Knowledge on Seatbelt Use among Commercial Bus Drivers in Makurdi Metropolis

Variables	Frequency N=173	Percentage %
Are you aware of the purpose of a seatbelt		
Yes	167	96.5
No	6	3.5
In your opinion, how effective is the use of a seatbelt in preventing injuries during an accident		
Very effective	121	69.9
Somewhat effective	26	15.1
Not effective	19	11.0
Don't know	7	4.0
What are the potential consequences of not wearing a seatbelt while driving		
Fines or legal penalties	38	22.0
Increased risk of injury or death in case of an accident	118	68.2
Risk of being stopped by the police	16	9.2
No	0	0
Don't know	1	.6
What is the legal requirement for commercial drivers concerning seatbelt in Nigeria		
Must use seatbelts all the time	125	72.2
Use seatbelts occasionally	20	11.6
Not sure	28	16.2

Table 3: Attitude Towards Seatbelt Use among Commercial Bus Drivers in Makurdi Metropolis

Variables	Frequency N=173	Percentage %
Do you believe wearing a seatbelt while driving is necessary		
Yes	140	80.9
No	33	19.1
What is your general attitude toward seatbelt use in your vehicle		
I always wear it	104	60.1
I wear it sometime	38	22.0
I rarely wear it	30	17.3
I never wear it	1	.6
Why do you wear a seatbelt		
For safety reasons	110	63.6
To avoid fines or legal trouble	57	32.9
It is a personal habit	4	2.3
It makes me feel more comfortable	2	1.2
I don't wear it	0	0
How do you feel about the enforcement of seatbelt use among commercial bus drivers		
Strongly support	88	50.9
Support	46	26.6
Neutral	32	18.5
Oppose	5	2.9
Strongly oppose	2	1.1
Do you think that seatbelt use should be made mandatory for both the driver and passengers in commercial vehicles		
Yes	122	70.5
No	7	4.0
Not sure	44	25.4

Table 4: Practice of Seatbelt Use among Commercial Bus Drivers in Makurdi Metropolis

Variables	Frequency N=173	Percentage %
How often do you wear a seatbelt when driving a commercial bus		
Always	105	60.7
Often	32	18.5
Occasionally	30	17.3
Never	6	3.5
Do you have seatbelt in your car		
Yes	164	94.8
No	2	5.2
Have you ever been involved in an accident while driving a commercial bus		
Yes	67	38.7
No	106	61.3
If yes were you wearing a seatbelt during the accident		
Yes	48	27.8
No	28	16.2
No answer(never been involved in an accident)	97	56.1
If you do not wear a seatbelt, what are the reasons for not wearing it		
No answer	58	33.5
I find it uncomfortable	27	15.6
I forget to wear it	30	17.3
I feel it is unnecessary for short trips	35	20.2
The seatbelt in the bus is not functional	7	4.0
I feel confident in y driving skills	10	5.8
I have never considered using it	1	0.6
Others	5	2.9
Do you encourage your passengers to wear seatbelts?		
Yes, always	98	56.7
Sometimes, when I remember	43	24.9
No, I don't encourage them	32	18.5
Are there any challenges you face in ensuring that all passengers use seatbelts		
Yes	71	41.0
No	102	59.0

Figure 1, 2 and 3 showing the knowledge, attitude and Practice Scores, respectively, of the respondents.

Table 5: Awareness and Training among Commercial Bus Drivers in Makurdi

Variable	Frequency N=173	Percentage %
Have you received any formal training on seatbelt use and road safety		
Yes	93	53.8
No	80	46.2
If yes, who provided the training (n=93)		
Employer/company	39	41.9
Government/ traffic authorities	48	51.6
Non – governmental organization	1	1.1
Others	5	5.4
Do you think more training or public awareness campaigns on seatbelt use would be helpful of commercial bus drivers		
Yes	130	75.1
No	5	2.9
Not sure	38	22.0
What do you think can be done to improve the use of seatbelt among commercial bus drivers in Makurdi? (open ended)		
Education, awareness, sensitization, training	109	63
Law enforcement	42	24.3
Others	22	12.7
Do you have any other suggestion to promote road safety and seatbelt use?(open ended)		
Education, awareness, sensitization	78	45.1
Law enforcement	30	17.3
Road construction	26	15
Conducting vehicle check	2	1.2
No Idea	37	21.4

DISCUSSION

More than three-quarters of the participants are aware of the use or purpose of seatbelts. This is similar to the study conducted in Trinidad, where most of the participants also demonstrated good knowledge.⁵ Furthermore, most of the participants agreed that seatbelts are very effective in preventing injuries during accidents, and injuries could be a consequence of not wearing seatbelts. However, few agree that it's due to legal penalties and fines. Comparing this to a study done in Gondar (Ethiopia), there was a higher level of knowledge registered on the purpose of seatbelt use.⁶ This knowledge gap might be due to a lower level of orientation and education among drivers in Makurdi metropolis. On the legal requirement of seatbelt use there's lower level of knowledge in Trinidad than in Makurdi metropolis. This might also be attributed to a lower level of orientation and education among drivers in Trinidad.

In Makurdi metropolis, most drivers demonstrated a positive attitude toward seatbelt use, acknowledging its role in reducing injury severity during road traffic

accidents. Similar findings were reported in Ethiopia,⁶ whereas a less favourable attitude was observed among drivers in Sokoto.⁷ This survey also shows that a little below two-thirds of commercial drivers in Makurdi metropolis always wear a seatbelt, while less than a percent of the participants do not wear a seatbelt at all. This is higher compared to a survey carried out in Ilorin⁸ and Owo, Southwest Nigeria⁹ where a little below half of the participants indicated they always used seatbelts. This difference might be due to the availability of training by Federal Road Safety Corps officials and non-governmental institutions in Makurdi metropolis when comparing these studies. Close to two-thirds of commercial drivers in Makurdi metropolis wear seatbelts for safety reasons and one-third of drivers wear it to avoid fines and legal troubles. Although the study in North Gondor Ethiopia⁶ revealed that three-quarters of the drivers wear seatbelts for safety, which is better in comparison, the study in Illorin, Nigeria⁸ revealed that most of the drivers wear seatbelts to avoid fines.

With respect to the enforcement of seatbelt use, the majority of the drivers in this survey indicated support.

In comparison to the study in Ilorin⁸, a slightly lower proportion of participants support the enforcement of seatbelt use. In addition, most commercial drivers feel seatbelt use should be made mandatory for both drivers and passengers, few do not agree to this, while others are not sure. A poor or good attitude towards the use of a seatbelt could have a major effect on public health. This is because the attitude of an individual is capable of influencing their behavior; thus, a poor attitude towards the use of seat belt could be an indication for poor compliance which in turn could be deleterious in cases of accidents. It was discovered that more than half of the commercial drivers surveyed in Makurdi metropolis always use seat belt when driving. This is better compared to Ilorin⁸ where less than half of the commercial drivers always use their seatbelt while driving. However, there's a large difference with respect to drivers in the United Kingdom which revealed almost complete compliance with use of seat belt while driving.¹⁰ This actually shows a wide gap in knowledge and practice.

Majority of the participants in Makurdi metropolis have seatbelts in their car, a little above one third of the participant have been involved in some form of road traffic accident while close to two third deny any involvement in accident during the course of their work. Most of the drivers were wearing seatbelt when it happened, and it's evident that seatbelt helped to prevent injuries as most of the drivers wearing seatbelt sustained little or no injuries. The main reason some drivers in this study do not wear seatbelts is that they feel it is unnecessary for short trips. This is in contrast to the study done in Ilorin where frequent stops were ranked the most important factor and driving short distance was almost the least reason⁸. In Sokoto, more than half of drivers complained that seatbelts make them uncomfortable.⁷

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The level of seatbelt use is relatively low compared to the level of good knowledge and attitude among drivers, which is particularly true for instances where drivers operate on short trips, in less heavy traffic, or for passengers, as they complain that seatbelts stain their

outfits. Government and non-governmental organizations should launch more targeted campaigns aimed at commercial drivers, focusing on the safety benefits of seatbelts and addressing misconceptions about their use. The Federal Road Safety Corps should increase the enforcement of seatbelt laws, with penalties for non-compliance, particularly for commercial bus drivers, and incentives should be given to compliant commercial drivers.

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